
IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT METHODS IN ENTERPRISES

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Annotation. The main purpose of this article is to study theoretical and practical aspects in the innovative management of industrial enterprises in the developing era of innovation and eliminate their main disadvantages.

Keywords: hierarchical levels, market economy, innovation sphere, innovation service, complex functions, material resource.

Innovation management system that determines the competitive advantage of the enterprise it is the main combination of economic, legal and other factors. Competitiveness of the enterprise it determines its position in the market. Competitive Enterprise, first of all, strategic potential the correct development of its elements; in addition, the enterprise has its own competitiveness how better than the environment to maintain and keep it at a high level it will have to answer a number of questions about whether it should be used. Therefore, the current enough about what the management system should be in day processing enterprises no information. However, deep in all branches of the agro-industrial complex during the years of development one of the reasons for the occurrence of the crisis changed the management structure. Therefore, the network principle of the processing industry management structure is modern it is known that it does not meet the requirements. First, the network aspect of the wider divisions development and formation of labor costs in narrow specialized activities scientific does not guarantee based production. Staff manpower, however combined functions are implemented only at the enterprise level. Secondly, the provision of personnel for each branch of various industries it is necessary to prepare deeper. However, in most cases, the level of knowledge of

employees is established does not meet the requirements; on the management of the processing industry in the form of an industrial unit leading to a decrease in the level of Management, which determines the monitoring activities of state bodies coming; thirdly, too hierarchical levels of management, power distribution, implementation of management decisions and acceptance of orders are unreasonable in the number of groups leads to an increase; Fourth, the imbalance of sections is the same as in each network causes a recurrence of functions, which gives the total functionality of the workforce leads to a significant increase, in technological, organizational, economic and other activities participation also leads to an increase in management costs and management decrease in efficiency. At the same time, production in a market economy any companies that carry out their activities are subject to complex functions, including, comprehensive market research, sales organization, Customs and legal work, Advertising, Research and with forecasting, financial provision, Organization of financial and commercial activities must be combined. accounting, organization and control of money circulation, Organization of lending, taxation, calculations and payments, in addition to other budgets it is necessary to develop funds, effectively introduce new computer technologies. Such by combining functions, a certain part is done objectively at the regional level should be increased.

Therefore, a good product is not enough for company managers, they are new focusing on the emergence of technologies and not lagging behind competitors for them they must plan to include them in their enterprises. Innovation here implementation of management includes: innovative program and plan analysis, monitoring and implementation of new product development; creation of new product review of the project; conduct a single innovative policy, developed in these areas coordination of activities of release units; Innovative Service program providing financial and material resources; innovative by qualified personnel services. From an idea to a solution to complex innovative problems formation of temporary working groups up to the production of the product chain must. The competitive role of processing enterprises in the market today determines the attitude of the consumer towards the enterprise and its products, which affects the volume of

sales in the market. Enterprises with an innovative management system installed on it can reach. This system is aimed at achieving goals; innovation to production promotion of introduction; Planning; Organization of work on the introduction of innovations quot; production problems, from idea to production of product chains control over the introduction of innovations. Effective activities of the agro-industrial complex in the region processing industry management system, which has a significant impact on maintenance one of the improvement measures: territorial industrial management bodies are all necessary complete statistics on the constant addition and updating of information creation of a data bank, as well as state interests in the field of current legislation it can solve many basic tasks necessary to express; developed increase the share of deep processing of their products in the composition of countries and the commodity market approximation of the structure; maximum use of production capacities processing of agricultural products produced in the region for the purpose of, also, its implementation abroad on the basis of the volume of production and new technology improving the competitiveness of technical production in other possible areas, assistance in rapid modernization; territorial and nominal technical organizations provision of raw materials and materials from sources.

In addition, enterprises improve the management of innovative processes

clearly responsible for the implementation of relevant activities that can create a mechanism must have a system of structure, deadlines, resource provision, action plans. Regulatory documents issued by the enterprise at different levels of the organizational structure, it should also be clearly defined in the management structure, in financing. In the enterprise the organization and management of the innovation process can be attributed to a number of factors, including in the enterprise depends on the level of development of innovative potential. Enterprise Innovation the level of development of potential, in which working literacy, research, developments in the situation (research in the complex function of promoting innovation in all departments and developments), system stability, on the introduction of a new product. innovative projects characterized by sufficient funds for

implementation. Development of innovative potential an important role in the process of innovation development should be played by the Department. This division is distinct from has an organizational structure and specially trained personnel with special status must be. New opportunity of organizational plan in the management structure of the Innovation Unit it is necessary to create a special organizational unit that allows you to perceive as. Of the division. innovation activities include analysis of information about innovation, strategic applications and development of promising solutions, planning new innovations, production includes adjusting the process to new rules. In addition, the organization has highly qualified scientific staff will be able to keep trade secrets, to ensure that the end users focus on needs and initial production opportunities for scientific research they need to be sure to focus. Because to scientific research of qualified personnel continuous improvement and modernization of production methods of directed activities serves to do.

Conclusion

Therefore, innovative development in the organizational structure of the processing industry the introduction of the division is decisive for the further development of the innovative activities of the enterprise of importance. Department of innovation development structure Department of innovation development with the head who performs the duties of the manager of innovative development and is special includes specialists who clearly define the main tasks of preparation must.

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